

Chapter 4 in the *Bhāvacūḍāmaṇi*, edition

(25r,1)

athetyādi | yatet prayatnam āśrayet | sā sarva ityādi | aṣṭg raktaṃ tadvarṇam |
 svāduśabdena madhuram ucyate | (2) kaṣāyaṃ harītakyaḍi | kṣatajaṃ śoṇitaṃ |
 tadgandhety arthaḥ | bāṇāḥ śarāḥ | amṛtā guḍūci | kāṣās tṛṇaviśe(3)śās tannicayena
 vyāptam | yāsu dhūlir | yāsāṃ bhūmīnām | udagādiplava ity ādigrahaṇāt prāci gṛhyate |
 ta(4)thā ca kiraṇādaḥ prāgudak plavati | tena pūrvottaranimnā yāḥ siddhās tāḥ śreṣṭhāḥ |
 saṃkīrṇāḥ kali(5)kardamaviṣṭānvitā yās tās tathāphalā iti saṃkīrṇaphalā eva | vyālabilāni
 sarpavivarāṇi | valmī(6)kāḥ prāguktāḥ | uśarāḥ sikatākālilam majjā pūtipradhānam
 kardamam | khātavarīdīpagaṇāś ca bhū(7)mayo yās tāḥ śasyante | tatra khātaparīkṣā yathā
 khātasya mṛtpūraṇād yasyāṃ mṛdadhikā bhavati sottamā | (8) samā yasyāṃ sā madhyamā
 | ūnāta yasyāṃ sādhamā | yad uktaṃ kiraṇe

hastamātraṃ purā khātvā pūraṇād adhi(9)kā śubhā |
 samā yā madhyamā jñeyā kanyasā yā na pūrayed ||

iti | vāri jalaṃ yasyāṃ śīghraṃ śamaṃ yāti sātra (10) śobhanā cireṇa yasyāṃ sā
 śreṣṭheti vāriparīkṣā | dīparīkṣā yathā apakvagaḥopari gṛhapūrṇe tathā(11)vidha eva
 śarāvake pūrvādidikkrameṇa vaktramantritāḥ śvetādivartīś catasraḥ prajvālya yasyāṃ tās
 ca(12)tasro 'pi ciraṃ jvalantyas tiṣṭhanti sā śobhanā | śrīmatpiṅgalāmate 'py ayam evārtha
 uditāḥ | tad uktaṃ ta(13)tra āmakumbhopariṣṭād ityādi | yasyāṃ pūrvavarjaṃ āsāṃ
 praśamas tadā sāpi śreṣṭhaiva anyathā tv aśu(14)bhā ity
 evaṃprakāreṇa | āsāṃ ityādi | āsāṃ madhyāt sarvagaṇāsambhave yā |

25r,1 varṇam] em.; varṇā C 25r,2 bāṇāḥ] em.; bāṇāḥ C • guḍūci] em. guḍūci C

25r, 2-3 kāṣās tṛṇa] em.; kāṣāvarma C

25r,3 yāsu dhūlir] em. Sanderson; yāsurdhūlir C • udag] em.; ugaḍ C

25r,4 nimnā yāḥ] em. Sanderson; nimnāyā C

25r,8 khātvā] conj. Sanderson; khaṇḍa C

25r,9 śīghraṃ] em.; śāghraṃ C

25r,11 catasraḥ] em.; catatraḥ C

25r,13 yasyāṃ] em. Sanderson]; yadidaṃ C • āsāṃ] conj. Sanderson; yāsāṃ C

4.x+1 (25r,14) yai vālpadoṣādhikagu(15)ṇā ca bhūmiḥ sā śalyadoṣanivṛttyartham śodhyā |

4.x+3 (25r,15) śodhyakṣetra ityādi | śodhanīye kṣetre manovyāpā(16)reṇa vāstoḥ śarīraṃ kalpayitvā tadaṅge śalyaṃ jānīyāt nimittataś cihnāt | tad evāha

4.x+4 (25r,15) pāpa i(25v,1)tyādi | pāpāḥ prāguktās teṣāṃ anyatamo graho horāgataḥ san vāstugaṃ śalyaṃ nivedayati kathaya(2)ti | horāśabdena meṣādiko lagna ihocyate | yadi kaścit pāpo lagnagato na bhavati tat kiṃ śalya(3)m asti na vety āha kendra trikoṇa ityādi | kendraśabdena tatkālādītāc caturthasaptamadaśamasthānā(4)ni | yad uktaṃ sūkṣmajātake

kendracatuṣṭayakaṇṭakalagnāstadaśacaturthānām |
saṃjñā

iti (Laghujātaka, Rāśiprabhedādhyāya 18) | tatrastho vā (5) pāpagrahaḥ śalyaṃ vāstugaṃ nivedayati | athavā trikoṇasaṃsthaḥ sa evāvedayati | trikoṇaśabdena (6) navamapañcame vivakṣite | yad uktaṃ tatraiva

navapañcame trikoṇa

iti (Laghujātaka, Rāśiprabhedādhyāya 16) | yadi vā rāśīsvareṇa vibhūṣito yukto (7) bhavati tadā tan nivedayatīti sambandhaḥ | rāśīśvarāḥ prak pratipādītāḥ | itthaṃ śalyāstitvaṃ jñātvā (8) tadviśeṣajñāpanāyāha

x+1,25r,14 śodhyā] em. Sanderson; śādhyā C

x+3,25r,15 śodhanīye] corr. Sanderson; śobhanīye C

x+3,25r, 16 tadaṅge] em. Sanderson; tadaṅgaṃ C

• nimittataś cihnāt] em. Sanderson; nimittatacihnāt C

x+4,25v,1 vāstugaṃ] em.; Sanderson; vāstu C

x+4,25v,3 kendra trikoṇa] em.; keṃdratriṇa C

x+4,25v,4 kendracatuṣṭayakaṇṭakalagnāstadaśacaturthānām | saṃjñā] em.;

kendracatuṣṭayakaṇṭakalagnāstadaśacaturthānām | saṃjñā Laghujātaka,

Rāśiprabhedādhyāya 18; kendracatuṣṭayaṃ kaṇṭakaṃ ca lagnāstadaśacaturthānām saṃjñā

C

x+4,25v,5 sa eva vā] conj.; saēvā C x+4,25v,8 jñāpanāyāha] em.; jñāpa[[ra]]nāyāha C

x+4,25v,6 rāśīsvareṇa] conj. Sanderson; rāśīśvara C

x+4,25v,7 śalyāstitvaṃ] conj. Sanderson; śalyāsthitavaṃ C

4.x+5 (25v,8) **drekkāṇa** ityādi | idaṃ ślokadvayaṃ granthavistārasamaye | drekkāṇaḥ sāyudho ya(9)dy udgacchati tal lohasya vikāraṃ lauhaṃ śalyaṃ vijānīyāt | suvarṇādayo 'ṣṭau lohaśabdenocyante (10) sāyudhadrekkāṇaś cokto bṛhājātake varāhamihireṇa

kaṭyāṃ sitavastraveṣṭitaḥ kṛṣṇaḥ śakta ivābhi(11)rakṣitum | raudraḥ paraśuṃ samudyataṃ dhatte raktavilocanaḥ pumān ||

iti (Bṛhājātake 27.1) | sārgale ca drekkāṇe sati tad eva śalyaṃ (12) niḡaḡānvite tad eva | sāḡnau ca bhasmāḡgāro vā | sapāśe ca carmakhaḡḡātmakeṃ śalyaṃ | sapāśo drekkāṇas tatro(13)kto yathā

vastrair vihīnābharaṇaiś ca nārī mahāsamudrāt samupaiti kūlam | sthānacyutā sarpaniveṣṭi(14)tāḡḡī manoramā vṛścīkarāśīpūrvā ||

iti (Bṛhājātake 27.22) |

4.x+6 (25v,14)sadaḡḡe dārujaṃ śa(15)lyaṃ vijānīyāt | sadaḡḡaś ca yavanenokto yathā

nīlābaro nīlavapuḥ pracāḡḡo daḡḡāyudho nīla(16)kirīṭamālī | valītarāḡḡaiś ca gavākṣitāḡḡo meṣas ṭṛīyaḥ kalikālakalpa ||

iti | ratnahemā(26r,1)diyukte tat kṛte ratnahemādimayam eva śalyaṃ avagantavyam | ādigrahaḡḡān maṇimuktāhārā ḡṛhyaṃ(2)te | ratnayuktaś cokta eva pūrvam bhūṣito varuṇabahvaḡḡaratna ityādi

kravyāda ity | kravyam apakvaṃ māṃsaṃ ta(3)d atti bhakṣayati yaḥ sa tathā | tasmin sati śalyaṃ asthisambhavaṃ boddhavyam | kravyādo drekkāṇaḥ siṃha(4)jambukādiḥ so 'pi darśita evāḡḡau | saviṣāde vā mārake himsre sa ca viṣādayukto yadi lagne dṛśya(5)te | tathā ca yavanaḥ:

himsro naraḥ kāñcanavarmadhārī bile nidhāneṣv ahiyoga † yājvaḥ | ratnasvarūpā(6)rthavid etya dūraṃ sa gupyate svair muṣitaḥ sahāyair || iti |

x+5,25v,9 lohaśabdenocyante] em.; lohaśabdebocyanto C

x+5,25v,10 varāhamihireṇa] em. Sanderson; varāhamihire C

x+5,25v,12 niḡaḡānvite] em.; niḡaḡānvitaṃ C

• bhasmāḡḡāro] em. Sanderson; bhasmāḡḡārau C

x+6,25v,14 sadaḡḡe dārujaṃ śalyaṃ vijānīyāt] em.; sadaḡḡe dārujaṃ śalyaṃ

vijānīyāt sadaḡḡe dārujaṃ śalyaṃ vijānīyāt C x+6,25v,15 valīta] em.; balīta C

x+6,26r,4 saviṣāde] em. Sanderson; saniṣāde C

4.x+7 (26r,6) tathānyena prakāreṇa śalyaparijñānam āha | (7) **āyair ityādi** | dhvajo dhūmas tathā siṃhaḥ śvā vṛṣaḥ khara eva ca gajo dhvāṃkṣaś ca śāstrajñair āyā jñeyāḥ | (8) sthirāś carā iti | āyair vā boddhavyam | kiṃbhūtaiḥ | ata āha **ādityagatiniścitais tathā pradī(9)ptadhūmitādisthair** iti | ādityāgatiniścayam eteṣāṃ buddhvety | athavā kiṃ bahunoktena | āyair ve(10)ti ślokadvayasya sārḍhasya bāhulyena jyotiḥśāstrānabhiññatvāt satyam arthaṃ na vidmaḥ |

4.x+13 (26r,10) **śvaśṛgā(11)lādaya** ityādi | ādigrahaṇān mārjāranakulamūṣakaprāyāḥ kṣudraprāṇino **viśantaḥ kṣetram** ity avagan(12)tavyam | punar api śalyaparijñānāntaram **tadāśetyādi** ācāryayajamānaśilpinām anyatame **tadā(13)śāsamsthita** iti | tasya vāstupuruṣasya āśā dik dakṣiṇā vāmā vā | tasyāṃ sthite sati tasmi(14)n **dehe** śarīre yat tanoḥ svalpaṃ kaṇḍūyanam tenaiva jānīyāt tadaṅgagaṃ śalyam |

4.x+14 (26r,14) etad eva sphuṭayitum āha (15) **mūrdhna** iti | **mūrdhny** eva tasya vāstupuruṣasya **pumardhataḥ** | kiṃcidūnād dhastadvayād adha iti vakṣyamāṇena sambandhaḥ (26v,1) | **asthi** ca śalyam bhavati |

4.x+15 (26v,1)**kāṣṭham** ityādi | idānīm āsye kaṇḍūyite sati kāṣṭhaṃ śalyam hastadvayena khānitenā | (2) **grīvetyādi śṛṅkhalaiva** śalyam tribhir hastaiḥ | athavā tatraiva grīvāyāṃ **mārjārasya** sambandhipañjaraṃ karaṇ(3)kaṃ puruṣārḍhapramāṇakhātāt |

x+7,26r,7 khara] em.; khaga C

x+7,26r,8 sthirāś carā iti āyair] em.; sthigaścarāitiitirāyair C

• kiṃbhūtaiḥ] em.; kiṃbhūtair C

x+7,26r,9 pradīptadhūmitādisthair] em.; pradīptadhūmitādisthaiḥ MY A;

pradīptadhūmitādiksthair C

• ādityagati] em. Sanderson; ādityagata C • buddhvety] em. Sanderson; buddhety C

• bahunoktena] em. Sanderson; bahunoktena C • āyair] conj. Sanderson; nāyair C

x+13,26r,10 śvaśṛgālādaya] em.; śvaśṛgālādayaḥ MY A; śvamṛgādaya C

x+13,26r,11 teṣāṃ] em.; tetram C

x+13,26r,12 pariññānāntaram] em.; pariññānaṃtaram C

• manyatām] conj.; manyatam C

x+13,26r,13 dakṣiṇā] em.; dakṣiṇā[[mā]] C

x+13,26r,14 kaṇḍūyanam] ed. Sanderson; kaṇḍūṣaṇam C

• tenaiva jānīyāt tadaṅgagaṃ] em. Sanderson; temavājānīyātadaṅgagaṃ C

x+14,26r,15 vakṣyamāṇena] em. Sanderson; vakṣyamāṇe C

x+15,26v,1 hasta] em.; ha C • pañjaraṃ] em. Sanderson; pañjanaṃ C

4.x+16 (26v,3)**pravāletyādi** | **śrutidvaye** karṇayugale **pravālakam** iti vidrumaṃ **kāñcanam** (4) **vātha rajatam** śalyaṃ **narārdhāt** khānitāt | **mauktikam** ityādi | akṣṇor **mauktikam tadvad** iti narārdhapramā(5)ṇād eva | **varāhetyādi pṛṣṭhabhāge**

kaṇḍūyita iti prakṛtaṃ | **varāhakūrparam** iti sūkarasya sambandhī jānvā(6)khyo 'vayavaḥ śalyam | **trihastāt tv** iti vakṣyamāṇakam apekṣyam |

4.x+17 (26v,6)**ghrāṇa** ityādi | **ghrāṇa** iti nāsāyāṃ **gandha(7)vad dravyam** śalyaṃ trihastād eva | bhruvoḥ **kācaprāyam** | **trihastāt tv** itihoktaṃ pūrvoktadvayasyāpy apekṣitam ity u(8)ktam | **daśaneṣv** iti dantavikāre saty abhṛakam vijānīyāt | **tatheti** trihastād eva |

4.x+18 (26v,8)**bāhvoḥ** puruṣasambandhi bāhva(9)sthiśalyaṃ kaṭipramāṇakhātāt | **krode** vakṣasi **pāśavam** ity **asthi sārhdhād dhastāt** samuddharet |

4.x+19 (26v,9)**pārśve** (10) pārśvāsthy eva śalyaṃ hastadvayāt | **urasi** hr̥tpradeśasambhavam evāsthiśalyaṃ **hastārdhāt** uddharet | ha(11)stād **adhah paryañkāṅgam** iti khaṭvāvayavaṃ śalyam |

4.x+20 (26v,11) **kaṭipradeśe vikārataḥ āyasam** iti † caimaram † **kīlam** (12) śaṅkuprakhyam śalyam uddharet | **trihastāt kṛṣṇaloham** iti † caimaram † eva śalyaṃ **trihastāl lakṣayet** |

4.x+21 (26v,13) hastapramāṇakhātasyādastāt **triloham** iti suvarṇarajatātāmramayaṃ śalyam uddharet |

x+16,26v,3 karṇa] em.; ka[[ra]]rṇa C x+16,26v,5-6 sambandhī jānvākhyo 'vayavaḥ] em. Sanderson; saṃbaṃdhijānvākhyamavayavaḥ C

x+17,26v,7 bhruvoḥ] em.; bhruvauḥ C

x+16,26v,6 apekṣyam] em. Sanderson; upekṣyam C

x+18,26v,8 bāhvoḥ puruṣasambandhi] conj. Sanderson; puruṣasambāndhi C

x+18,26v,9 sārhdhād] em.; sārād C

x+19,26v,11 paryañkāṅgam] em.; paryañkāṅgam MY A; paryamkākam C

• khaṭvāvayavaṃ] em. khaṭvāvayave C • śalyam śalyam] em.; śalya C

x+20,26v,11 āyasam] em.; āyasam MY A; āvāsam C • kīlam] conj.; kīrṇam C

after 4.x+21 (26v,13) sphijīti | (14) kaṭyāḥ pṛṣṭhabhāgāvayaḥ
 sphikśabdenocyate | tasmin kaṇḍūyite puruṣārdhapramāṇakhātāt ṭaṅka(15)kam iti
 trapuprāyaṃ śalyam | ūrudvaye sāraṃ ca tat kāṣṭhaṃ hastāt sārdhāt | jānvoḥ sthūṇāyā eva
 sthū(16)laṃ kāṣṭhaṃ kṣurādi veti | nāpitabhāṇḍaṃ kṣuraṃ | ādigrahaṇād † rāyārātiṃ †
 kartarīṃ veti vikalpato ha(27r,1)stasyādhasāt | samuddharet iti śeṣaḥ | gulphe
 tribhāgenonād dhasāt turaṅgasyāṅgaṃ turaṅgaḥ pādaḥ | tam ādiśe(2)j jānīyāt | pādaṃ
 dvairadaṃ dviradasya kariṇa idaṃ dvairadaṃ | dantyādi | ādigrahaṇād dhayā ghyante |
 evaṃprāyaṃ śalyaṃ (3) kiṃ cid dhasād adho lakṣayet pāde kaṇḍūyite satīti prakṛtam |

after x+21,26v,14 kaṇḍūyite] em. Sanderson; kaṇḍūyitaṃ C

26v,15 ūru] em.; uru C 26v,15-16 sthūlaṃ] conj. Sanderson; sthūṇaṃ C

26v,16 kāṣṭhaṃ] em. Sanderson; kāṣṭha C

27r,1 turaṅgasyāṅgaṃ] conj. Sanderson; turaṅgasyāyaṃ C • pādaḥ] em.; pādas C

27r,2 dantyādi] conj. Sanderson; daṃtādi C • dhayā] em.; dhāyā C

27r,3 prakṛtam] em. Sanderson; prakṛtī C

(27r,3) aṅguṣṭha iti tasya pādasyaiva prakṛtatvāt ā(4)rakūṭam iti rītiśalyam | tatheti kaṇḍūyanaparāmarśāya | pādopayogi vā carma mocoṭakādi śalyam uddha(5)ret | hastenoneti sthitam eva yāvan nāpavādaḥ | kaniṣṭhāyā vikṛtau satyām | ghoṣam iti kāmśyaśalyam boddha(6)vyam | madhyamāvīkṛtāv aṅguṣṭhavad iti yad aṅguṣṭhe śalyam ārakūṭādy uktaṃ tad eva | pādātale padyam carma śalyam | (7) pāde hitaṃ padyam | proktāni yāny aṅgāni teṣām ūrdhvādho yāny āsannāny upāṅgāni teṣu kaṇḍūyiteṣu satsu (8) tanmayān iti proktāvayavoktān śalyaprakārān uddharet | yady evam suvarṇarajatādīnām katham śalyam tv amukta(9)pūrvam | tatrocyate śalyānām anantatvād iyattā paricchettuṃ na śakyate | paramārthatas tūkteṣu pradeśeṣu yad yatroktaṃ (10) tat tatraiva śalyam ity atrānyad vidyamānam api na doṣavad iti ratnahemādīnām evāyaṃ niyamaḥ | tāvanmātram ityā(11)dī | uktapramāṇanikhātād yāvad eva śalyadarśanam bhavati tāvanmātram tato 'nantaram mahim śodhayet | yad veti (12) pakṣāntarāśrayaṇam | pānīyadarśanaparyantaṃ yāvad veti vikalpanārthaḥ | tām aśmetyādi | tām mahim karo hastaḥ (13) pūryate yena sa karāpūraḥ tais tathāpramāṇair aṣṭabhir aṣṭāṅgulā mṛd antarā yeṣām taiḥ saṃsādhyeti susamān(14)tarasahām ca niṣpādyā | tatheṣṭaplavām iti | pūrvottaraplavaiva śreṣṭhaplavā sarvasaṃhitāsu kathitā yataḥ tām (15) tathāvidhām kuryāt | anantaram vakṣyamānopapattyā vāstuvartanāyām sthitān vakṣyamānābhidhānān (16)surān yajet | chāyetyādi | golo madhyapradeśe lāñchanabimbādih | tatrastho yo 'sau śaṅkus tena karaṇabhūtena (27v,1) nītaṃ yac chāyālakṣmadvayaṃ pūrvāparadigudbhūtaṃ tasmād diśam jñātvā | dhruvavedheneti ślokasya tadvad eva jyotiḥ(2)śāstrasāpekṣatvād arthaṃ satyaṃ na vidmaḥ | vāstusvarūpaparijñānāyocyate | prajānām ityādi | cakṣuṣo 'patyaṃ (3) cākṣuṣo brahmasutaḥ | tadasvāsthyam iti | bhūtakṛd ity umāpatih | jagaddhito viśvahitakārī |

27r,4 rīti] em.; rīti C • tatheti] em.; tathaiti C

• parāmarśāya] em.; parāmarśāya C 27r,5 kaniṣṭhāyā] em.; kaniṣṭhāyā C

27r,5-6 boddhavyam] em.; boddhavyam C

27r,6 aṅguṣṭhavad] em.; aṅguṣṭhovad C • ārakūṭātmakaṃ] em.; ārakūṭātkaktaṃ C

27r,7 āsannāny] em.; āsannāni C

27r,8-9 amuktapūrvam] em.; amuktampūrvam C

27r,10 vidyamānam] em.; virdyamānam C

27r,11 yāvad] em. yāvat C • mahim] em.; mahi C

27r,13 antarā] em.; aṃtarāṃ C

27r,15 vāstuvartanāyām] em.; vāsturvattanāyām C

27r,16 bimbādih] em.; bimādīs C • śaṅkus] em.; saṃkus C

27v,2 vāstu] em.; vastu C • pariññānāyocyate] em.; pariññānāyocyate C

(27v,3) rajjvetyādi (4)rajjvaṣṭakam eva mahāpāśās tathā vakṣyamānābhidhānam yad vaṃśadvitayaṃ tena tena ca vāstuṃ pīḍitaśarīraṃ kṛtvā sa (5) eva śaṃkaro 'nantaraṃ tac caturaśraṃ kṛtavān | atra vakṣyamānābhidhānānām vṛttaśaḍaśrāṣṭāśrādīnām prāsā(6)dānām vāstudevatāpadavibhāge pūjanādi katham iti ye codayanti teṣāṃ anenaiva ślokenottaraṃ | yasya ka(7)sya cit prāsādasya prathamam uktaṃ vāstudeham sampūjya tataś cikīrṣitaprāsādasampādanam | anyac ca (8) caturaśrād eva kṣetrāt kṣetrāntarānām abhivyaṅgīrṣā | tathā ca śrīmatkirāṇe

sarveṣāṃ caturaśraṃ tu kṣe(9)traṃ kṣetraṃ samantata
(not traced)

iti | tadvapur ityādi | jāgarti tiṣṭhati | vāstor anvarthatāpratipādanāyāha devetyādi | (10) tadvapuṣi yato devā adhivasanti tato vastūcyate | kiṃ ca vasatyāṃ gṛhe nityam eva saṃnidhānato 'pi iṣṭe(11)tyādi | marmaṇām rakṣaṇād abhipretaguṇapraṭhanārtham | arakṣaṇād vedhāt tv anyathā bhavati | taddehā ityādi | (12) yās taccharīre nādyo viṃśatiḥ | prāṇo vāyuh | taddevatā gṛhavāstos tasyaiva vasatyāṃ saṃnidher ity anena (13) prathamam apekṣitatvāt | īrita ity udīritaḥ | manorathetyādi tāś ca manorathādyāḥ śāntyantā daśa (14) prācyā iti pūrvānanāḥ somabhāgād uttarāyā diśaḥ | antakāntam iti dakṣiṇām diśaṃ yāvad avasthi(15)tāḥ hi bhādyā hiraṇyāntā daśottarānanāḥ | ity evaṃ viṃśatiḥ | etāś ca pīḍitā nāmasadṛśārthakṣa(16)ya hetavo bhavanti | rakṣitā guṇaṃ kāryaṃ kurvanti |

27v,4 mahāpāśās tathā] conj. Sanderson; mahāpāśastayā C

• vāstuṃ] conj. Sanderson; vā C

27v,5 'nantaraṃ] em.; naṃtaraṃ C 27v,7 cikīrṣita] em.; cikīrṣi[[[kī]]]ta C

27v,8 sarveṣāṃ] em.; sarveṣā C 27v,9 jāgarti] em.; jāgatī C

27v,10 saṃnidhānato 'pi] em.; sannidhānatopi C

27v,11 marmaṇām] em.; marmāṇām C

27v,12 vāyuh] em.; vāyus C • vasatyāṃ] conj. Sanderson; vāsatyāṃ C

agnīṣometi | āsām viṃśatisaṃkhyātānām | yā ma(28r,1)dhyā iti | madhyebhavāḥ
 ṣaṇ nāḍyas tanmadhyataḥ suṣumṇāḥ | pūrvāmnāyanāḍīdaśakād ādyaṃ nāḍitrayaṃ (2)
 tathottarāmnāyād ādyaṃ nāḍitrayaṃ | evaṃ ṣaṭ | īśānadigbhāge diśaḥ pradeśa eva vāstor
 īśamūrdhāpava(3)ktraka iti vakṣyamāṇavacanataḥ ṣaṭ tāḥ sauṣumṇāḥ | vāmabhāge
 saptaidyaḥ | dakṣiṇabhāge sapta pain(4)galyaḥ | anyac cāgrege durgapurāda
 vāstvantaraprastārasamaye sphuṭikariṣyati | ekādaśasirābhinne (5) sauṣumṇāḥ prāgvad
 udgatāḥ | aṣṭau aṣṭau bhavanty aidāḥ piṅgalās ca mahāsirā | ity anena | yas tv ā(6)sām
 daśānām nāḍīnām madhyāt ṣaṭ sauṣumṇā nāḍyaḥ śiṣṭaṃ catuṣṭayaṃ aidāṃ piṅgalaṃ ca |
 punar apy ā(7)sām daśānām eveti vyācāṣṭe tenādhyātmasvarūpānabhiḥjñatayā ekasyaiva
 vāstudehasyāntaḥ śa(8)rīradvayaṃ idāpiṅgalāntaritasuṣumnādvayaṃ āveditaṃ bhavati
 vakṣyamāṇavacasām cāsaṃgatā(9)rthatā pradarśitā anyac cāsām daśānām eveti
 pratipādakaṃ viśeṣaṇaṃ nāsti | kevalaṃ nāmato nā(10)ḍivīṃśatikam ukhvā sarvāsām eva
 saṃgrahād āsām madhyāt † yatyuktaṃ † yat sūtrakṛtā tad devānām priyo (11) 'sau
 svarucitam evaṃ vyākarotu | āsām ityādi | āsām viṃśatisaṃkhyātānām padātiśayayogād
 bhūyāṃso (12) bahutarā vikārā vakṣyamāṇāḥ |

27v,16 saṃkhyātānām] em.; sāmkyātānām C

• yā madhyā] conj. Sanderson; yesādhyā C

28r,1 suṣumṇāḥ] em.; suṣumṇā C

28r,2 tathottarāmnāyād] conj. Sanderson; yathottarāmnāyād C • ṣaṭ] em.; ṣaḍ C

28r,3 • vāmabhāge] em. Sanderson; vāsabhāge C

28r,4 durgapurāda] conj. Sanderson; dugapurāda C

28r,5 piṅgalās] em.; piṅgalās C

28r,6 piṅgalaṃ] em.; piṅgalaṃ C

28r,7 daśānām] em.; daśānām C

28r,8 idāpiṅgalāntaritasuṣumnādvayaṃ āveditaṃ] conj. Sanderson;

idāpiṅgalāntaritaṃsuṣumnādvayenāveditaṃ C

28r,8-9 cāsaṃgatārthatā] conj. Sanderson; cāsagatārthatā C

28r,9 cāsām] conj.; casām C

28r,11 'sau] em.; sau C • āsām] em.; asām C • padātiśayayogād] conj. Sanderson;

paṭātiśayayogād C 28r,12 bahutarā] conj. Sanderson; bahukārā C

(28r,12) saṃkoca ityādi | svalpe 'pi vāstau † yat † padālpatve saty api
 tryātmaka(13)tvam iti suṣumṇeḍāpiṅgalātmakatvaṃ na nivartata ity arthaḥ | tiryag iti
 āgneyavāyukoṇasthi(14)to durjayanāmā vaṃśo dvitīyas tv īśānaniṛṭtikoṇastho durdharah
 | brahmetyādi | yatra kutracid iti (15) gehe stambhavinyāsaḥ | devagṛhe
 brahmaśilāvinyāsādāv aṇunā sarṣapamātreṇāpy aṃśenāvaśyam eva (16) parihartavyam |
 uktaṃ ca śrīmatkīraṇe

etaj jñātvā tu saṃśleṣaṃ sūtrāṇaṃ marma tad bhavet |
 jñeyaṃ madhyaga(28v,1)taṃ marma tasmād yatnena varjayet ||
 kṛtvā tat ṣoḍaśāṃśaṃ tu tatraikaṃ marma tat punaḥ |
 kṛtvā ṣoḍaśadhā sthānaṃ varja(2)yet tat sadaiva tu ||
 (KI 54.22c-24b)

iti |

28r,14 īśānaniṛṭtikoṇastho] em.; īśānaniṛṭtikoṇastha C

28r, 15 stambhavinyāsaḥ] em.; staṃbhavinyāsa C

• aṇunā sarṣapamātreṇāpy] em. Sanderson; aṇḍanāsarpapamātreṇāpy C

28v,1 ṣoḍaśāṃśaṃ] KI; ṣoḍaśāṃ C • ṣoḍaśadhā sthānaṃ] KI; ṣoḍaśadhāsyonaṃ C

28v,2 sadaiva] KI; sadeva C

samastetyādi | sarvanāḍīsamyakpātāḥ saṃniveśaviśeṣā bhavanti | te sandha(3)yaḥ
procyante | te vasatāv iti veśmani hatāḥ santaḥ kartṛsthapatisūrīṇām
anyatamasyāṅgasan(4)dhīnām saṃkoce nimittaṃ sampadyante | sūrīṇām ity ācāryāṅām |

28v,2 samyak] em.; sasyak C • pātāḥ] conj. Sanderson; pātaiḥ C

vaktretyādi | eteṣu pradeṣeṣu vaktrādyeṣu kī(5)lakyādyam vivartāntam
 rajjucatuṣṭayam avaboddhavyam | hṛdādyeṣu sadbhāvādyam yakṣyantam catuṣṭayam |
 parā iti (6) prathamam yāḥ proktās tās tripadāḥ paścāt proktāḥ ṣaṭpadā iti sthitam eva |
 rajjv ityādi | sampāta (7) iti saṃghaṭṭaḥ | aṣṭāṅgapañkajam ity
 aṣṭāvayavopalakṣitapadmalaṅkaṇanānumeyam | upaskṛta (8) iti pīḍite | triśūlam ityādi |
 koṇapradeṣeṣu vaṃśena nāḍidvayena cārthād evā † rdhakā † trayopalakṣitam tri(9)śūlam
 | tad evetyādi | tad eva triśūlam ubhayasthiter vajram jānīyāt kuḍyādair iti
 bhittiprabhṛtibhiḥ | vaṃ(10)śetyādi | vaṃśena rajjvā ca koṇapradeṣeṣv eva saṃgatam iti
 trikoṇākārā saṃgatir yasya | tadardhe(11)tyādi | saṃpuṭārdhena halākāram marma bhavet
 | padetyādi | rajjubhyām eva padamadhye catuṣṭayam yat tat svasti(12)kākhyam marmety
 arthaḥ | rajjuvaṃśottham ityādi | tadrūpam eva rajjuvaṃśābhyām utthitam |
 mahāsvastika(13)m ity | etāvān eva viśeṣaḥ | mahābhayetyādi | śuddham iti | catuṣkoṇam
 eva | † yatpadanivāsakṛdbhavatī(14)madhyāhni yat te † | svaprāntetyādi | svaprānte
 nāḍīnām yaḥ sampātas tena trikaṭā nāma marma bhavati [Cf. SŚ vol. 4, p.49, 65a, line 9:
 svaprāntanāḍīsaṃpātas trikaṭam] yataḥ (15) tat tryātmakam triśūlākārād ākārāntareṇa |
 prasūter iti prajāyāḥ | pañcātmakam ityādi | tad eve(16)ti trikaṭayeva pañcātmakam
 pañcāvayavam mañibandhanākhyam | kośāśabdena gañja ucyate |

28v,4 pradeṣeṣu vaktrādyeṣu] conj. Sanderson; pravaktrādyeṣu C

28v,5 yakṣyantam] em. Sanderson; yakṣyante C • pureti] conj. Sanderson; parā iti C

28v,6 tās] em.; tāḥ C 28v,8 koṇa] conj.; koṇe PI 8.25a; kau C

• vaṃśena] conj. Sanderson; vaṃśa C

28v,9 bhittiprabhṛtibhiḥ] conj. Sanderson; prakṛtibhiḥ C

28v,11 halākāram] em. Sanderson; tulākāram C • yat tat] conj. Sanderson; tattat C

28v,12 rajjuvaṃśottham] conj. Sanderson; rajjuvaṃśoktam C

28v,13 etāvān eva viśeṣaḥ] em. Sanderson; etāvāneviśeṣaḥ C

28v,14 svaprāntety] em.; svaprānta SŚ; svapnāmtety C

• svaprānte] em.; svaprānta SŚ; svapnānte C • sampātas] em.; sampātas SŚ; sampāta C

28v,15 ākārāntareṇa] conj. Sanderson; ākārām?reṇa C

(29r,1) etānīti

mahāmarmasandhimarmapañkajatriśūlavajrasaṃpātahalasvastikamahāsastika
 śuddhapadatri(2)kaṭāmañibandhanākhyāni dvādaśamarmākhyāni | yadi kartā varjayet tat
 kārakasahito yathābhilaṣita(3)m āpnoti | tasyetyādi | tasya vāstudehasya prāgbhavaṃ
 dakṣiṇaṃ āpyam iti paścimam udbhavam uttaram viṣṭabhye(4)ti adhiṣṭhāya | prācyām
 ityādi | ekāṃseti | yady api vaṃśarajjubhiḥ padam ardhīkṛtaṃ tathāpi tatsakalatvam
 e(5)vāṃśatvenaikasya devagrhasya devagrhavāstoḥ devānāṃ keṣāṃ cid ardhapadānām
 ardhāṃśatvena vakṣyamānatvā(6)t | brahmā madhya iti | paryantakoṣṭhakāvṛtyām īśādyā
 ditiparyantā devā dvātriṃśat | madhye tu brahmā | ma(7)rīcir ityādi | asmād iti brahmaṇa
 eva pūrvasyām diśi marīciḥ ṣaṭpada iti vakṣyamāṇena sambandhaḥ | (8) mṛtyujid
 dakṣiṇāśāyām | āpavatsa ityādi | nābhasvatyām rājyakṣmety atra pāṭhakramānapekṣa
 ārthaḥ kramo(9)nuṣṭheyah | tenendraṃ prathamam nairṛtakṇe vinyasyānantaram
 vāyukṇe rājyakṣmā vinyāsyā iti | tadvad e(10)veti | yathāpavatsādayo dvipadās
 tathāivāpādyāś catusro devatāḥ | jayaśūlināv iti indrajayarudradā(11)sau | tebhyo 'nantarā
 ity āpavatsādivacatuṣkavinyāsād anantaram śaṅkarādiṣv evāvaśiṣṭeṣu padeṣv etā
 nya(12)syā ityārthaḥ | catusra ityādi | bahir vāstor īśādikoṇeṣu catusro rākṣasyaḥ |
 mahāntam iti vṛddham | arbha(13)kam iti bālam | kṣetrāśrayāṇāṃ devānāṃ kiyatī
 saṃkhyeti āśaṅkānirāsāyāha kṣetretyādi | pañcaka i(14)ti pañcacetvāriṃśad ityārthaḥ |
 katham iti cet tad eva dvātriṃśat tāvad īśādyā ditiparyantā
 brahmamarīcivi(15)vasvanmitrapṛthavīdharāpāpavatsasavitṛsāvitrendrajayarudradāsā
 trayodaśa | itthaṃ pañcacetvāriṃśad bhavanti | yatra kutra cid iti sarveṣāṃ
 vakṣyamāṇacatuḥśālādigrhāṇāṃ |

29r,1-2 trikaṭā] em.; trikaṭa C

29r,3 vāstu] em.; vastu C • prāgbhavaṃ] em. Sanderson; prāgbhāvaṃ C

• paścimam] em.; paścisam C

29r,4 ekāṃseti] conj. Sanderson; ekāṃśā C • yady] em.; yadi C

29r,5 ardhāṃśatvena] em.; ardhōśatvena C

29r,6 brahmā] em.; bahmā C • koṣṭhakāvṛtyām] em. Sanderson; koṣṭhakāvṛtṭyām C

• paryantā] em. Sanderson; paryamta C • devā] em.; devāḥ C

29r,8 mṛtyujid dakṣiṇāśāyām] em. Sanderson; mṛtyurjī dakṣiṇāśā C

• rājyakṣmety] em.; rākṣayakṣmety C

29r,9 nairṛtakṇe] em.; nainṛtakṇe C • vinyāsyā] em.; vityāsyā C

29r,10 yathāpavatsādayo] em.; yathāpavatsāddayo C • catusro] em.; catusro C

29r,11 āpavatsādiva] conj. Sanderson; āpavatsādeva C

• anantaram] em.; anaṃdaram C

29r,12-13 arbhakam] em. Sanderson; arbakam C

29r,15 sāvitrendra] em.; sāvitraindra C • trayodaśa | itthaṃ] em.; trayodaśetthaṃ C

(29r,16) bāhyasthiticatuṣkadvayasahi(29v,1)tās tripañcāśad eva |
 stambhabrahmaśileti ślokaḥ pūrvoktānuvādaḥ | devagr̥havāstur ucyate | navaprācyā (2)
 ityādi | navaprācyā iti | prāntāntarbhāvitāḥ ity anyasyām prāntam anyasyām antarbhūtam
 tasyā apy anyasyā i(3)ti yāvat | uktaṃ catuṣṣaṣṭipadāni kṣetre sampadyante sarveṣu
 vakṣyamāṇeṣu mervādiprāsādeṣu | yad āha:

catuḥ(4)ṣaṣṭipadaṃ kṣetraṃ samastasuradhāmasu

iti | tatra ca ditiś ceśāś ca khakṛṣānū ity antarikṣāgnī mṛgaś ca piṭṛ(5)nāmā ca
 rogākhyāś ca vāyuś cety aṣṭau koṇārasaṃśrayā ity ardhakoṇasthitayaḥ | śeśāś tu
 caturviṃśati(6)r bāhyāvṛtyāṃ padikā iti prakṛtam iti | uktaṃ ca śrīmatkīraṇe:

ditiśāś cāntarikṣo 'gnir mṛgaś ca piṭṛ(7)saṃjñakaḥ |
 pāpayakṣmā ca rogaś ca koṇāvāsthā divaukasaḥ |
 parjanyaś ca
 (KI 54.31-32a)

29r,16 dvaya] conj.; dva C 29v,2 prāntāntar] conj.; prātāntar C
 • anyasyām antar] conj.; anyāsāmaṃtar C
 29v,3 catuṣṣaṣṭi] cataṣṣaṣṭi • vakṣyamāṇeṣu] conj.: vakṣyamāṇe C
 29v,3-4 catuṣṣaṣṭi] em.; catuṣṣaṣṭi C
 29v,4 dhāmasu] em.; dhāmasv C • khakṛṣānū] em.; khakṛṣānū C
 • antarikṣāgnī] em.; aṃtarikṣastrī C
 29v,6 cāntarikṣo 'gnir] em.; aṃtarikṣognir C
 29v,7 parjanyaś ca ity] em.; parjanyaścety C

ityādyuktā ete tv ekapadā jñeyā i(8)ti yāvat | koṇabhṛto 'ṣṭāv ity āpavatsādayo
 'ṣṭau bāhyadevavad iti parjanyaḍayo yathā padikā ityarthah | (9) prāgvad eva
 marīcyādyāḥ pūrvavat ṣaṭpadā eva kiṃ tu sthānacatuṣṭayavaicitryeṇa |
 parjanyaḍyāvṛtyām a(10)dhaḥ pādacatuṣṭayam tadadhaḥ padadvayam | evaṃrūpeṇa
 ṣaṭpado marīciḥ | evaṃ vivasvanmitrapayodharāḥ | i(11)ttham api koṇabhṛto 'ṣṭau padikā
 bhavanti | evaṃ vaṃśau vasupadāv ity aṣṭapadau | arthasiddhau
 catuṣṣaṣṭipa(12)datvenaiva vāstoḥ | idānīm devabhāvasthityanurūpatvenānumeyo
 vāstupuruṣo boddhavyah | iti tadartham ucyate (13) brahmanābhir ityādi | brahma nābhau
 yasya | uktaṃ ca brahmā catuṣpado madhya iti | nābhiś ca madhyasthānam eva |
 śrī(14)matkīraṇe 'pi:

brahmā nābhigataḥ proktaḥ
 (KI 54.26c)

iti | pīṭṛpād iti | nairṛtakōṇasthitaḥ pīṭṛnāmā devah | ta(15)trāsyapādau |
 śrīmatkīraṇe 'pi:

nairṛte caraṇadvayam
 (KI 54.25b)

iti | īsamūrdhetīśānakōṇe mūrdhā śiro ya(16)sya | kīraṇe 'pi:

īśāne 'sya śiro vāstoḥ
 (KI 54.24c)

iti |

29v,10 marīciḥ] em.; marīcir C

29v,11 bhavanti] em.; bhavanty C

29v,12 anurūpatvenānumeyo] conj. Sanderson; ānurūpakenānumeyo C

29v,13 brahmā] em.;brahma C

29v,14 proktaḥ] em.; prokta C

• devah] em.; devas C

29v,15 nairṛte] em.; nainṛte C

29v,16 vāstoḥ] em.; vāstor C

(29v,16) āpavatsaka iti | āpābhidhāno vaktrasthāne 'rthād eveśā(30r,1)nakoṇād adhaḥ koṇasthiter asya | tadvatsaḥ kandharā ity āpavatsaḥ kandharā kaṇṭho yasya tena | yugmabhṛd iti | (2)koṇadvayadharāv arthataḥ proktaśiṣṭau savitr̥sāvitrau tathā rudrarudradāsau savyāsavyau pāṇi | kir(3)aṇe pi:

savitā hasto 'sya
(KI 54.25a)

iti | ditiparjanyaśabdārtha iti | ditiparjanyaḥ karṇau | śabdo 'rthaḥ prayojanaṃ ya(4)yoḥ karṇayos tau yasya | jayādityaṃsayugmaka iti | jayākhyāḥ aditiś ca tau skandhau yasya | r̥gyendrāv iti | r̥(5)gyādayaś ca ṣaṭ tathendrādayaś ca ṣaṭ yathāsaṃkhyenaiva vāmadakṣiṇabāhū yasya | rakṣodiksthayugmeśeti | (6) nair̥ṭadiksthaṃ yad yugmaṃ koṇadvayaṃ tasya yāv īsau tau gūlphe yasya | rogapūṣākhyeti | rogākhyāś ca tathā (7) pūṣākhyāś ca jānvaṅge yasya sa rogapūṣākhyajānvaṅga ity arthaḥ | marīcyavanibhṛd iti | marīcis tathā pṛ(8)thivīdhara etau stanau yasya | mitro vivasvān iti | mitras tathā vivasvān ūrupradeśo yasya | itthaṃ vāstupu(9)ruṣo 'yam adhomukho jñeyaḥ | asyāṅge savyāsavya iti | asya vāstor yat savyam aṅgaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ yac cāsavyaṃ vā(10)maṃ tatra svavasthitā iti svadigbhāgāparityāgena suṣṭhu kṛtvāvasthitā devāḥ | marmetyādi | sūkṣmāṇi yā(11)ni marmasthānāni anuktāni tāni svamarmabhyo vijñāya śreyaskāmo varjayet |

- 29v,16 āpavatsaka] em.; āpavatsakā C • iti] em.; ity C
 30r,1 tadvatsaḥ kandharā] em. Sanderson; tadvatsakaṃdharā C
 • āpavatsaḥ kandharā] em. Sanderson; āpavatsakaṃdharā C
 30r,2 rudrarudradāsau] conj. Sanderson; rudrarudradāsau ca C
 30r,3 'sya iti] em.; syeti C • śabdārtha] conj. Sanderson; śabdārthā C
 • śabdo 'rthaḥ] em. Sanderson; śabdārthaḥ C
 30r,4 karṇayos tau yasya] tentative conj. Sanderson; karṇayor eva C
 30r,5 saṃkhyenaiva] em.; saṃkhyenaiba C
 • rakṣodiksthayugmeśeti] conj. Sanderson; rakṣodiksthayugmeneti C
 30r,6 nair̥ṭa] em.; nair̥ṭa C 30r,7 aṅga] em. Sanderson; artha C
 30r,9 asyāṅge] em.; asyāge C
 30r,10 svavasthitā] em.; svavasthita C • suṣṭhu] em.; suṣṭu C
 30r,11 tāni]; {tāni} C

vāstvantaram ucyate | ekādaśai(12)kādaśa nāḍyo 'sya pūrvottarāmukhāḥ | prāgvad eva
sauṣumṇyaḥ | prāgvad iti ṣaṭ | ekādaśabhya ekādaśabhyas tisra(13)s tisraḥ sauṣumṇyaḥ |
śiṣṭā aṣṭāv aṣṭāv aidāḥ paiṅgalāś cety evaṃ | śatapadam kṣetram bhavaty eva | kiṃ
nimittam | i(14)ty ucyate durgapurāṭṭālakabhūmiṣv iti | khetaketi grāmaśabdasya
svapadopāṅgatvād gobalīvardanyāyena (15) svalpo grāmaḥ | nivāsādiṣv ity ādigrahaṇād
vihārārāmabāhyāliprabhṛtiṣv api tatra devatānyāsaḥ | (16) grahāś catuṣpadā iti skandādyāś
catvāraḥ | pūrvavad iti dikṣv evety arthaḥ | kiṃ tu bāhyapaṅktyantar eṣa
cānya(30v,1)vāstor asya viśeṣaḥ | pañcāṃśabhūtanāyaka iti | carakyādyāḥ koṇeṣu
pañcapadāḥ |

30r,12 ṣaṭ | ekādaśabhya] tentative conj. Sanderson; ṣaḍ eva ca C

30r,13 paiṅgalāś] em.; paiṅgāś C

• bhavaty eva] tentative conj. Sanderson; bhavateva C

30r,14 gobalīvardanyāyena] em. Sanderson; balīvardanyāyena C

30r,16 padā] em.; pradā C • skandādyāś] em.; skandhādyāś C

• antar eṣa] conj. Sanderson; antarereṣa C

30v,1 nāyaka] em.; nāyakā C

4.y+1 (30v,1) **brahmādayas** tu deva(2)gr̥havāstūktāmśāḥ | **rajjvādaya** ityādigrāhaṇād vamaśāv api | itthaṃ bāhyāvṛtiṃ graharākṣasiniṃmittaṃ (3) varjayitvā antar yac catuḥṣaṣṭipadaṃ kṣetraṃ tat suragr̥havāstūktavibhāgadevam

4.y+2 idānīm deśavāstur ucyate | (4) **catustrimśad** ityādi | catustrimśatā sirābhiḥ pūrvottarāmukhībhir viracite kṣetre sati navāśī(5)tyā cāṃśakānām ādhikyena yad uktaṃ **sahasram** aṃśakānām evotpadyate iti prakṛtaṃ eva | tatra devatā(6)vinyāsāyāha

4.y+3 (30v,6) **tatra sārdham** ityādi | dve **pañktī** ardhapañktiś ca | kimarthaṃ tatparityāgaś ced ata āha **rakṣogra(7)hātmika** iti | carakyādiskandādirakṣograsaṃbandhinī

padārdhāntaritair iti pañktyardham antare prave(8)sārthaṃ **parityajya** tadantaritair **navabhir bhāgaiś** ca parityaktair ity adhyāhriyate | tato **navabhir bhāgaiś tri(9)guṇair** iti saptaviṃśatyā | **guṇair** iti tair api triguṇitaiḥ | etad eva viśeṣayaty

4.y+4 **ekāśītipado bra(10)hmeti** | **koṇeśāḥ ṣaṭkṛtīśvarā** iti | ṣaṇṇaṃ ca kṛtiḥ ṣaḍguṇitatvam | ayam arthaḥ | āpavatsādayaḥ (11) pūrvoktavāstunirdeśāt koṇanāthāḥ ṣaṭtrimśatkoṣṭhakādhipatayaḥ | **catuṣpañcāśad īśānā** iti | (12) marīcyādayas tu catuṣpañcāśad adhināthāḥ | **navadhāpara** iti | **apare** digbhṛta īśato ditiparyantāś ca | (13) brahmaṇo 'nantaraṃ pañktiṣaṭkaṃ parityajyānantaraṃ pañktidvayaṃ yad avaśiṣyate tatra pratyekaṃ **navadhethi** nava(14)koṣṭhakādhiṣṭhānās ta ity arthaḥ |

4.y+5 durgapurādivāstor asya ko viśeṣo yena yathā tatra skandādyāḥ kṣetrāntara eva (15) proktās tathāpīha te | tad āha **viśeṣo vyāptijaḥ** | iti nānyat kiṃ cid viśeṣas **tā eva yato devatāḥ** kevalaṃ (16) vyāptikṛta eva | asmin bahupadabhājo devās tatra tv anyathā | atha citāvāstur vipannadīkṣitānām dāha(31r,1)sthāne yaḥ kriyate yad vakṣyati dīkṣitānām kṛtā citir iti kimbhūtaḥ |

y+1,30v,2 bāhyāvṛtiṃ] em.; bāhyāvṛtiṃ C y+1,30v,3 devam] conj. Sanderson; devaḥ C y+1,30v,4 sirābhiḥ] em. Sanderson; sirāti C

• pūrvottarāmukhībhir] em. Sanderson; pūrvottarāmukhīti C

y+2,30v,4-5 navāśītyā] em.; navatiraśītyā C y+2,30v,5 cāṃśakānām] em.; cāśakānām C

• ādhikyena] em.; ādhikyenaṃ C y+3,30v,6 sārdham] em.; sārdha C

y+3,30v,6-7 rakṣograhātmika] em.; rakṣograhātka C

y+3,30v,9 triguṇitaiḥ] em.; triguṇitair C

y+4,30v,12 marīcyādayas] em.; parīcyādayas C • navadhāpara iti] em.; navadhāpareti C

• apare] em.; apara Cy+4,30v,13 'nantaraṃ] em.; naṃtaraṃ C

y+4,30v,14 koṣṭhakādhiṣṭhānās ta ity] conj. Sanderson; koṣṭhakādhiṣṭhātety C

y+5,30v,15 tathāpīha te] conj. Sanderson; tathāpīte C

• vyāptijaḥ] em.; vyāptija C • viśeṣas] conj. Sanderson; viśeṣās C

y+5,30v,16 eva | asmin] em.; evāsmiṃ C y+5,31r,1 yaḥ] em. Sanderson; yat C

tadartham āha **bhūtavargeti** | pañca(2)viṃśatikoṣṭhakopalakṣite tatra **kṣetre madhye pañcakā** iti | madhyebhavaṃ madhyam | tasmin pūrvādiṣu catasṛ(3)ṣu dikṣu tathā sarvamadhyakoṣṭhake cety arthaḥ | tatra **kṣmā** bhūmiḥ saketi brahmaṇā saha | vinyasyed iti vā(4)kyabhedena kriyādhyāhāraḥ |

4.y+6 **catuṣke nairṛta** iti | nirṛter idaṃ yan nairṛtaṃ catuṣkaṃ tatra **viṣṇusahitaṃ** (5) **vārīti** varuṇaṃ nyaset svāśrayor iti | yā yasya svakā dik | **tadvad** iti catuṣka eva | īsarudrasamā(6)śritāv iti yathāsaṃkhyena |

y+5, 31r,1 bhūtaḥ] em.; bhūto C

y+5,31r,3 vinyasyed] em.; vīnyasyed C

y+6,31r,4 nairṛta] em.; nairṛta C • nirṛter] em.; nirṛter C

• nairṛtaṃ] em.; nairṛtaṃ C

y+6,31r,5 svāśrayor] conj.; svāśrayau MY A; svāsayor C

y+6,31r,5-6 samāśritāv] em.; Sanderson; samāśritov C

4.y+7 (31r,6) **vyoma śambhor** iti | **aiśānyām** diśi catuṣke śambhunā saha vyoma | vinyase(7)d ity arthaḥ | **vedalakṣite** catuṣsaṃkhyopalakṣite indrayamavarūnasomāḥ **sthitā** iti

4.y+8 svadigsthā(8)ne **padaikavyāpakatvenety** api yaṣṭvaivam iti evaṃ darśitabhāgena **devatāvyāptau** satyām saṃpūjya |

4.y+9 **rā(9)ṣṭrabhūtānām** iti | ṣaḍvidhasyāpi bhūtavargasya vivṛddhir bhavati | **vikalā tadvipattaya** iti ta(10)dakaraṇād vipattiḥ sthitaiva | idāniṃ sadoṣabhūśuddhaye vāstvantaram ucyate **navaka** ityādi | **navaketi** (11) navakoṣṭhakānkite kṣetre **brahmapradhānānām** lokapālānām brahmasthānataḥ prāgīśāntaṃ krameṇa brahmādi(12)lokabhṛtpūjane kṛte

4.y+10 **bhūmir** apadoṣā bhavati svāmīna **iṣṭapradā** bhavatītyarthaḥ | atraivārthe vika(13)lpena vāstudvayaṃ ślokenāha **grahān** ityādi | ādityamukhāt ketvantān grahān | **eteṣv** iti navasu saṃ(14)pūjya bhūmiḥ śuddhā bhavatīti

4.y+11 athavaiteṣv eva padeṣu ca **navadhā** pratyekaṃ padapravibhaktiyā tān eva grahān ma(15)dhyāt prabhṛti prāgvat pūrvādīśāntakrameṇa śrīpauṣkaroktanavanābhayāgavad ityarthaḥ | athavāstrayā(16)gaḥ **athetyādi** | **kṛtvā bhūmeḥ parigraham** iti vāstupūjāsthānataḥ sthānāntare bhūparigraham astra(31v,1)kalaśavāridhārāvinyāsādinā kṛtvā śivāstrakalaśe saṃpūjya tato

4.y+13 **maṇḍape vedikāmadhye** ity ukta(2)pradeśe śivaṃ maṇḍalasthaṃ saṃpūjya mantravid iti prāguktasvarūpo vidvān | etenānyatrāpy uktaṃ nājño bhrāntaḥ (3) sasamdeho gurur bhāvavivarjita iti | **kṛte cittarpaṇa** ity agnikāryaṃ homaṃ ca mantratarpanārthaṃ kṛtvā chidra(4)nirharaṇāya ca prāyaścittahomam api kṛtvā saṃhitāyāḥ pūrṇāhutim prakṣipyānantaram pūrvoktavidhānena

y+7,31r,6 iti | aiśānyām] em.; itīśānyām C • catuṣke] em.; catuṣkaṃ C
y+9,31r,8-9 rāṣṭra] conj. Sanderson; suṣṭhu MY A; rāṣṭrasya C
y+9,31r,9 vikalā] em.; vikalās C
y+9,31r,10 sadoṣabhūśuddhaye vāstvantaram] conj. Sanderson; sadoṣabhūśuddha evāstvantaram C
y+10,31r,12 iṣṭa] em.; iṣṭa MY A; śreṣṭha C • pradā] em.; padā C
y+10,31r,13 eteṣv] em.; eteṣu C y+10,31r,14 bhavatīti] em.; bhavatīty C
y+13,31v,1 maṇḍape] em.; maṇḍapa C
y+13,31v,2 śivaṃ] conj. Sanderson; śiva C • mantravid] em. Sanderson; śāstravit MY A; mantravad C

4.y+14 (31v,5) **vāstudehaṃ nādivibhāgena vartayet | tatretyādi**
 īśānādikrameṇāvāhanādīpūjanaṃ kṛtvā **balim** ya(6)thā vibhāgena vakṣyamānaṃ dadyād ācārya
 etenānuṣṭhānakrameṇety arthaḥ | **īśānadevatāir** iti īśā(7)no devataiṣāṃ tair utpattivācakair
 mantrair ity arthaḥ |

4.y+15 **sāmānyair** iti vaidikaiḥ "imā rudrāya sthiradhanvane" [= RV 7.46.1a] (8) "kad
 rudrāya pracetase" [= RV 1.43.1a] "tryambakaṃ yajāmahe" [= RV 7.59.12] ityevamādyair
 ṛgvedapaṭhitais tathā "rudrākhum te paśuṃ karomi" [Kāṭhakaśaṃhitā 9.7; 36.14 (only in Kāṭhaka
 in this form)] ityevamādyair ya(9)jurvedapaṭhitai rudrasāmabhiḥ sāmavedapaṭhitais ca
 athavetaraiḥ sve kalpe ye vihitās tair ity arthaḥ | (10) **ghṛtākṣatā** iti ghṛtaṃ yavās ca |

4.y+16 **padmetyādi | padmāmbv** iti padmam ambu ca **ghananāthāya** parjanyaḥ |
 4.y+17 **vitāna**(11)m ityādi | **vitānam** karaktakaṃ **dhūmram** nīlakapiśaṃ **aṃśave**
 ravaye | **satyāyetyādi** |

4.y+18 **dānamudrayeti** (12) pradhānābhīmukhīkṛtahastena | **madhv** ityādi | **palam**
 apakvaṃ māṃsam |

4.y+20 **gandhān** ityādi | **gandhān** iti sarvagandhān | (13) **jihvām** ityādi | **vaihaḡim** iti
 pakṣisambandhinīm | **mṛḡāyetyādi** | yavāṅkurāṇi | **pitṛbhya** ityādi | (14) **kṛsarodanam** iti
 tilakena kṛsarākhyā siddhā |

4.y+21 **dauvārika** ityādi | dantadhāvanam | **sugrīvetyādi darbha**(15)**kam** iti
 darbhaveṣṭaram |

4.y+22 **pracetasa** ityādi | **vāriruham** iti padmam | **pūrvavad** iti dānamudrayaiva |
surām i(16)ti surāpratīvastutvena

4.y+23 **nāgakesaracūrṇāni** suprasiddhāni dravyatvena **phaṇine** nāgāya

4.y+24 **bhakṣyā**(32r,1)**ṇītyādi | bhakṣyāṇīty** anekākārāṇi ghṛtapūrikādīni |

bhakṣyādītrayaṃ yathāśaṃkhyena **mukhyādi**(2)**bhyas tribhyaḥ | mantramudrāprayogata** iti
 pūrvoktānuvādaḥ |

4.y+25 **ṛgyāyetyādi | śālūkam** utpalamūlam | **alopya** i(3)tyādi | **lopya** vā iti lopikāḥ |
pūrikā iti sviṣṭakṛto bhojanaviśeṣaḥ |

4.y+26 **modakān** ityādi |

4.y+27 raktacanda(4)naṃ sugandhadravayayuktam | **haridrānnam** ityādi | haridrāmiśram
 annaṃ dhautamudgam | **miśrāna**(5)**m** ityādi | **miśrānnam** iti miśr † aiva †

tajjayāyetyādiindrajaḡyāya |

y+14,31v,6 dadyād] em.; dadyāt C y+14,31v,7 devataiṣāṃ] em.; devatā eṣāṃ C • utpatti] conj.; upatti C
 y+15,31v,7 dhanvane] em.; dhanvine C y+15,31v,8 pracetase] em.; pracetasai C • paṭhitais]
 em.; patais C

• karomi ityevamādyair] em. Sanderson; karomīvamādyair C y+15,31v,9 paṭhitais] em.; paṭhatais C
 y+20,31v,14 kṛsarākhyā] conj. Sanderson; sarākhyā C y+22,31v,15 surām] em.; sumam C
 y+24,32r,1 anekākārāṇi] em.; enekākārāṇi C • pūrikādīni] conj.; pūragharikādīni C
 y+24,31v,2 mantramudrāprayogata] conj. Sanderson; mantramudrāprayogataḥ MY A; maṃtraprayogata C
 y+25,31v,2 mūlam | alopya] conj.; alopyaḥ MY A; mūlam tallopya C y+25,31v,3 viśeṣaḥ] conj.
 Sanderson; viśeṣa C

y+27,32r,4 haridrānnam] em.; haritānnam C • annaṃ] em.; aṃnnaṃ C

4.y+28 (32r,5) **guḍaudanam** ityādi | **māmsavad** iti | tad eva **siddhānam**
māmsayuktam ru(6)drāya | **rājayakṣmaṇe** iti rudradāsāya |

4.y+29 **sāmiṣam** iti māmsayuktam annam | rudrasya punar ghr̥tena saha
vimiśritam iti viśeṣaḥ | **atisaṃsiddhān** ity atipakvān **māṣān vasumatībhṛte** pṛthivībhṛte |
īsetyā(8)di | āpāpavatsābhyāṃ yathāsaṃkhyena dadhikṣire | kiraṇe 'py uktam:

payodadhīśakṣe tv
(KI 54.53a)

iti |

4.y+30 **pañcagavyetyā**(9)di | punar api yo dadhīśabdaḥ |

4.y+31 sa majjavācakaḥ **pittam** ity āntaro māmsakhaṇḍaviśeṣaḥ |

4.y+34 **bāhyata** ityādi bāhya(10)taś carakyādyaṣṭakasya **evam** uktena krameṇa
balim dattvā tato 'nyaḥ **sārvakāmikaḥ** sarvakāmaprado baliḥ |

4.y+35 (11) mātṛmaṇḍalayuktagaṇebhyaḥ pratidinmukhaṃ
divyāntarikṣabhaumanivāsibhyo namaḥ iti **śabdaprayogataḥ** | dā(12)tavya ity arthaḥ |

4.y+36 **homa** ityādi | **homas** tu **svāhāpadāntair mantrair argho vaṣaḍantais**
tadvad iti vausaṭpadāntair eva | **mā**(13)**lyādī**yādigrāhaṇād vastrālaṃkārāḥ | tat sarvaṃ
namaskārayogena |

4.y+37 **japa** ityādi | pāṛthivabī(14)**jalakārasthaiḥ stambhananimittam japaḥ**
kāryaḥ | cāṭanam uccāṭanam tannimittam yakāro vāyubījaḥ tatrasthaiḥ (15) siddhyartham
saha visargeṇa visarjanīyena ye vartate taiḥ savisargair

4.y+38 dīptām ūrdhvādho rephasamyuktaih cchedanani(16)mittam chṛg iti yat
padaṃ tatprāntaiḥ puṣṭir āpyāyanam tannimittam [Note that this indicates the reading
cāṭane, against the reading uccāṭe of the Mūla MS.] vakāro **varuṇabījam** yataḥ |

4.y+39 **amṛtākṣarāṇi** (17) 1ṃ 2ṃ 3ḥ mṛtyuvijayāya etadakṣaragaiḥ | athavā sve
sve kalpe vihitā yā jātis tayā kṛtam upapadani(32v,1)mittam lakṣaṇam yeṣāṃ taiḥ |

4.y+40 **evam** ityādi | anivāritam ity avighnam ||

bhāvacūḍāmaṇau vāstupāṭalāś caturthaḥ

y+29,32r,6 sāmiṣam] conj. Sanderson; sāmiṣān MY A; sāmiṣānam C

y+29,32r,6-7 vimiśritam] tentative conj. Sanderson; viśliṣtam C

y+29,32r,7 viśeṣaḥ | atisaṃsiddhān] em.; viśeṣaḥ nātsaṃsiddhān C

• atipakvān] conj. Sanderson; apakvān C • pṛthivībhṛte] em.; pṛthivībhṛteprthivībhṛte C

y+29,32r,8 dadhikṣire] em.; dadhikṣireṇa C y+30,32r,9 yo] conj. Sanderson; payo C

y+34,32r,10 'nyaḥ] em.; nyaḥ C y+36,32r,13 vastrālaṃkārāḥ] em.; vastrālaṃkārās C

y+37,32r,13 japa ityādi] em.; japaītyādijapaītyādi C • pāṛthiva] em.; pāṛthava C

y+38,32r,16 chṛg] em.; chag C • bījam] em.; bījaḥ C

y+39,32r,17 1ṃ 2ṃ 3ḥ]conj. Sanderson [= oṃ juṃ saḥ]; 1ṃ 2ṃ 3ṃ C

• vijayāya etad] em.; vijayāyaitat C